

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ОСОБЕННОСТЬ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ САМООЦЕНКИ МЕДИЦИНСКОГО ПЕРСОНАЛА ПРИ КОРОНАВИРУСНЫХ ИНФЕКЦИЯХ COVID-19

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THE IMPORTANCE OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-ASSESSMENT OF MEDICAL PERSONNEL IN COVID-19 CORONAVIRUS INFECTION

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье представлен анализ специфики профессиональной самооценки студентов в образовательной среде. Актуальность исследования определяется формированием профессиональной самооценки в условиях новой коронавирусной инфекции, одной из острейших проблем на сегодняшний день. Авторами проведен анализ источников по проблеме исследования и вопросам развития профессиональной самооценки. Представлено тестирование, которое позволило определить уровень сформированности общей и профессиональной самооценки студентов, обучающихся на отделении «Сестринское дело».

ABSTRACT

The article presents an analysis of the specifics of professional self-assessment of students in the educational environment. The relevance of the study is determined by the formation of professional self-esteem in the conditions of a new coronavirus infection, one of the most acute problems today. The authors analyzed the sources on the problem of research and the development of professional self-esteem. The testing is presented, which allowed to determine the level of formation of general and professional self-esteem of students studying at the department of «Nursing».

Ключевые слова: самооценка, профессиональная самооценка, медицинский персонал, коронавирусная инфекция, профессиональное самоопределение.

Keywords: self-assessment, professional self-assessment, medical staff, coronavirus infection, professional self-determination.

One of the main goals of the healthcare system during the epidemic with COVID-19 coronavirus infection is to ensure high quality medical care for patients. The achievement of this goal depends crucially on the participation of nursing staff, including future specialists. High-quality medical care can be provided by an average medical worker who has high self-esteem, is motivated to work, and is confident in his ability to solve the tasks facing him. Important factors of motivation to provide high-quality medical care are respect for the medical worker in society, his high social status and material assessment of work and responsibility assigned to him [1].

The impact of the epidemic has just shown that such situations cause a pronounced change in the emotional state of people, which is quite vulnerable. In isolation, a person will almost certainly encounter a spectrum of various asthenic emotions in the form of fear and anxiety, aggression, as well as fear and anxiety for the health of their loved ones, for the future, after quarantine. Almost every person on the planet has faced such manifestations as loneliness, uncertainty, uncertainty about the future, which generates even greater anxiety and fear, which are projected by illogical and inconsistent actions of state administrative structures,

the receipt of contradictory information from the media.

The epidemiological situation also affected the students of medical schools, as they had to study and work in the conditions of a pandemic. This problem led to the fact that many students noted pronounced fear, constant anxiety and depression, as well as a sense of guilt if they could not cope with their emotions in a hospital setting. According to domestic and international data, a high level of workload and the threat of infection significantly increase the risk of professional burnout and emotional maladaptation in the form of symptoms of depression, anxiety and emotional distress in medical workers during a pandemic, which leads to a decrease in professional self-esteem [2].

Self-esteem is a person's knowledge of himself and attitude towards himself in their unity. Self-assessment includes the allocation of a person's own skills, actions, qualities, motives and goals of their behavior, their awareness and evaluative attitude to them.

Self-esteem, depending on its form (adequate, overestimated, understated) can stimulate or, conversely, suppress human activity. Inadequate, low self-esteem reduces the level of a person's social claims, contributes to the development of self-doubt, limits a

person's life prospects. Such self-esteem can be accompanied by severe emotional breakdowns, internal conflict, etc. Low self-esteem also damages society, since a person does not fully realize his strength and capabilities, does not work with full dedication.

The most important source of self-esteem development is the professional self-esteem of college students perceived by us as a reflection of their educational, professional history, the creation of a professional vision of themselves as a professional in the future. Today, in this regard, it becomes necessary to form professional self-esteem, since it is one of the universal internal and external mechanisms for improving efficiency, especially of a medical specialist: his decision-making, behavior in a team, work in a professional environment as a whole, as well as a system that actually affects the development of all professional skills, which subsequently leads to the establishment of personal and professional growth.

Readiness for professional self-determination, from the point of view of professional activity, is a unified personality trait, it promotes reflexive and independent decision-making in professional choice. Having carried out a theoretical analysis of professional self-determination as a socio-cultural and socio-psychological phenomenon, all this gives grounds to conclude that this is a complex unified character of a young professional [2].

According to the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard, one of the significant qualities of a future professional is a developed and formed professional self-esteem (personal, professional, educational, reflexive, etc.).

In 2022, during the period of practical training, students working in covid hospitals were tested among graduates who filled the bulk of the needs for the personnel of the secondary medical personnel of the healthcare system of the Kirov region. The experiment involved students of 6 groups from the III to IV year. The diagnosis was based on the method of self-assessment of the personality of A.S. Budassi. Testing was conducted anonymously to ensure a more reliable result. The analysis of the data obtained made it possible to determine the level of formation of general and professional self-esteem of students studying at the department of "Nursing". During the testing, we did not identify students with inadequately low self-esteem (below 16 points). But, nevertheless, the total number of students with inadequate self-esteem was slightly more than half of the respondents - 58%. Results below 37 points (inadequately low and low self-esteem) and above 66 points (high and inadequately high) were attributed to inadequate self-esteem. According to the results of the study, there was no inadequately low level of self-esteem among students, 9% of respondents showed a low level of self-esteem. At the same time, an inadequately high level of self-esteem was revealed in 28% of students, and a high level in 5%. Thus, the test

results revealed the presence of the problem of an inadequate level of formation of the general and professional self-esteem of students, as well as the need to search for a set of educational conditions and pedagogical technologies that form, first of all, the professional self-esteem of future medical workers in the process of training in secondary vocational education.

According to the recommendations on psychological support of target groups in a medical institution in the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic, issued in October 2020 by Academician of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Doctor of Psych.N. Y.P. Zinchenko, psychological support of secondary medical personnel should solve several tasks and take into account organizational difficulties associated with the working hours of nurses:

1. Information task. Improving the general psychological literacy of medical personnel. This task can be solved in the form of classes devoted to the psychological aspects of the disease, the peculiarities of the behavior of a sick person, the peculiarities of the experience of his relatives and friends.

2. The task of personal psychological study. This task can be solved in the form of targeted training programs aimed at developing skills of adaptation to work situations, at understanding existential problems that actualize in the process of work. And also in the form of regular support groups ("Balint groups"), where psychologically problematic work situations would be discussed. In addition, individual work in the form of psychotherapeutic consultations is also possible. Our experience has shown that it is this work that allows you to form a student's professional self-esteem.

Today, researchers are trying to assess the impact of COVID-19 on other vulnerable groups, including students of medical schools who provide all possible assistance in the fight against the pandemic, exposing their health. In addition, there is a need to develop mental health interventions that are time-limited, culturally sensitive, and can be taught to medical professionals and volunteers. Once developed, such interventions should be validated so that information regarding effective therapeutic strategies can be widely disseminated among those working in this field

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